

The multilingual aspect of citation contexts

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Outline

- 1 Introduction
- 2 Multilingual citation context analysis
- 3 Method and materials
- 4 Perspectives

Context

English was recognized as the dominant language of international science [Gordin, 2015] for a long time from 1967 and it continues to dominate global scientific activities to this day.

Figure: Graph of the languages in which science has been published from 1880 to 2005, plotted as a percentage of the global scientific literature.[Gordin, 2015]

Context

Non-English languages also account for a large number of publications and are being influenced by the hegemony of the English language in science.

- 1 [Albarillo, 2014] has used Scopus and JSTOR to explore the trends and language distribution of social science publications and found that about 10% social science publications were not written in English.
- 2 [Liu, 2017] shows that English is increasingly being used as the dominating language from natural sciences and social sciences to arts and humanities. Around 97% of the papers in SCIE, 95% of the papers in SSCI, and 73% of the papers in A&HCI during the past decade were in English.

Issues

- ① Probably the most prominent criticism is that citation analysis based on raw citation counts ignores the underlying reasons for the citation. [\[Ritchie, 2009\]](#)
- ② Language biases in research assessment :
 - (1) *Current research evaluation systems in many countries (especially in EU) set guidelines that encourage researchers to publish in prestigious or high-impact factor journals.* ¹
 - (2) Some studies are national science for a specific country.
 - (3) [\[Engels and Kulczycki, 2022\]](#) advocates the balanced multilingualism as an approach that supports taking language into account in all aspects of research assessment without prioritizing scholarly communication in any language over publications in other languages.

¹Taşkın et al. (2020) Science needs to inform the public. That can't be done solely in English

Consensus on reforming research assessment

- 1 "Boukacem-Zeghmouri, Chérifa (2022). Le champ bibliométrique questionné par le marché des indicateurs d'impact : évolutions socio-techniques, socio-économiques et enjeux épistémologiques. CIDE 2021."
- 2 *"Ideally, language is a non-issue in assessment. Researchers should be recognised and rewarded according to the results and the impact of their research"*²
- 3 *"The aim is for research to be evaluated based on intrinsic merits rather than on the number of publications and where these are published."*³
- 4 **Agreement on reforming research assessment** (July 20, 2022) : *"The assessment of research, researchers and research organisations recognises the diverse outputs, practices and activities that maximise the quality and impact of research. "*

²Pölonen et al. (2021) Multilingualism is integral to accessibility and should be part of european research assessment reform.

³Scoping report on research assessment by European Commission, Paris Call on Research Assessment in Open Science European Conference (OSEC) in 2022

Research uptakes

- 1 Does the choice of research language lead to biases in research assessment?
"in all kinds of expert evaluation procedures, the selection of assessment language can discriminate against researchers who are not native speakers or fully fluent in the given language(s)"⁴
- 2 Do we mobilise concepts identically from one language to another?
- 3 How to return to the text itself and consider language phenomena to extract relevant and useful information ?

⁴Pölönen et al. (2021) Multilingualism is integral to accessibility and should be part of european research assessment reform.

Citation context analysis

Many citation studies are conducted to better understand the citation process and the effectiveness of citation analysis in quality assessment : like **citation context analysis**

What does citation context mean ?

A citation context is defined as “that particular passage or statement within the citing document containing the references”
[Small, 1982].

[Small, 1982] noted that citation context analysis is typically used for two purposes:

- 1 to classify the types or functions of citations in texts
- 2 to examine “the semantic content of the citation passage to characterize the cited work.

Expanding the PhD research in the direction of multilingue

Subject : Study and classification of citation context in order to better understand citation behaviors

- ① Citation context analysis goes beyond traditional narrative and systematic reviews to better understand the impact of seminal works and influential authors.
- ② It is able to "... help scholars explore and describe—at a specific and detailed level—how important ideas are used by and spread from a source text to subsequent citing works.
[\[Anderson and Lemken, 2020\]](#)
- ③ The citation context can be used to classify the citation type or category to indicate how the papers were influenced by other cited papers.

Categorization of citation function

- | | |
|----|--|
| 1. | Cited source is mentioned in the introduction or discussion as part of the history and state of the art of the research question under investigation. |
| 2. | Cited source is the specific point of departure for the research question investigated. |
| 3. | Cited source contains the concepts, definitions, interpretations used (and pertaining to the discipline of the citing article). |
| 4. | Cited source contains the data (pertaining to the discipline of the citing article) which are used sporadically in the article. |
| 5. | Cited source contains the data (pertaining to the discipline of the citing article) which are used for comparative purposes, in tables and statistics. |
| 6. | Cited source contains data and material (from other disciplines than citing article) which is used sporadically in the citing text, in tables or statistics. |
- | | |
|-----|---|
| 7. | Cited source contains the method used. |
| 8. | Cited source substantiated a statement or assumption, or points to further information. |
| 9. | Cited source is positively evaluated. |
| 10. | Cited source is negatively evaluated. |
| 11. | Results of citing article prove, verify, substantiate the data or interpretation of cited source. |
| 12. | Results of citing article disprove, put into question the data as interpretation of cited source. |
| 13. | Results of citing article furnish a new interpretation/explanation to the data of the cited source. |

Figure: Spiegel-Rosing's Categories for Citation Motivations [Spiegel-Rosing, 1977]

Categorization of citation function

[Teufel et al., 2006] adapted an earlier manual classification scheme :

Category	Description
Weak	Weakness of cited approach
CoCoGM	Contrast/Comparison in Goals or Methods (neutral)
CoCoR0	Contrast/Comparison in Results (neutral)
CoCo-	Unfavourable Contrast/Comparison (current work is better than cited work)
CoCoXY	Contrast between 2 cited methods
PBas	author uses cited work as starting point
PUse	author uses tools/algorithms/data
PModi	author adapts or modifies tools/algorithms/data
PMot	this citation is positive about approach or problem addressed (used to motivate work in current paper)
PSim	author's work and cited work are similar
PSup	author's work and cited work are compatible/provide support for each other
Neut	Neutral description of cited work, or not enough textual evidence for above categories or unlisted citation function

Figure: Teufel's annotation scheme for citation function [Teufel et al., 2006]

Categorization of citation function

CiTO, the Citation Typing Ontology :

Factual relationships	Rhetorical relationships		
	Positive	Negative	Neutral
<i>cito:cites</i>	<i>cito:confirms</i>	<i>cito:corrects</i>	<i>cito:discusses</i>
<i>cito:citesAsAuthority</i>	<i>cito:credits</i>	<i>cito:critiques</i>	<i>cito:reviews</i>
<i>cito:citesAsMetadataDocument</i>	<i>cito:extends</i>	<i>cito:disagreesWith</i>	
<i>cito:citesAsSourceDocument</i>	<i>cito:obtainsSupportFrom</i>	<i>cito:qualifies</i>	
<i>cito:citesForInformation</i>	<i>cito:supports</i>	<i>cito:refutes</i>	
<i>cito:isCitedBy</i>	<i>cito:updates</i>		
<i>cito:obtainsBackgroundFrom</i>			
<i>cito:sharesAuthorsWith</i>			
<i>cito:usesDataFrom</i>			
<i>cito:usesMethodin</i>			

Figure: The 23 relationships between citing and cited document in CiTO
[Shotton, 2010]

Method

Where we can find citation context and how ?

" [\[Teufel and Elhadad, 2002\]](#) observe that citation classification has strong ties with rhetorical discourse structure analysis and note its consequent usefulness in tasks like text summarisation."

Identifying citation contexts in the rhetorical structure of scientific papers - IMRaD structure :

" The IMRaD structure often changes in some journals and these differences must be taken into account in order to compare the distribution of references along the text using an invariant measure" [\[Bertin et al., 2013\]](#)

Method

Where we can find citation context and how ?

Filtering the context sentences more intelligently - coreference resolution [Joshi et al., 2020], [Bertin et al., 2019]:

Figure: Coreference citation blocks. [Bertin et al., 2019]

Corpora

Objective : building a multilingual corpus

- **ISTEX** A reservoir of scientific archives at the service of French research, covering all disciplines with more than 25 million scientific publications and spanning a period of 700 years. [\[Collignon and Cuxac, 2017\]](#)

- It has developed a software tool chain for citation extraction that will be applied to existing databases of scientific literature and made available to researchers with a special focus on the German-speaking social sciences. [\[Hosseini et al., 2019\]](#)

- dataset which is composed of 7 journals in English in the field of science, technology and medicine. [\[Kamińska, 2017\]](#)

Perspectives

- ① A more multifaceted exploration of the citation context analysis, especially in the direction of exploring whether they are influenced by linguistic phenomena.
- ② Better understanding of language issues and their consideration in bibliometrics.
- ③ Possibility of taking language into account in all aspects of research assessment and then increase the impact of other languages in scientific research.
- ④ Echo the Helsinki Initiative on Multilingualism in Scholarly Communication.⁵

⁵Helsinki Initiative on Multilingualism

Thank you for your attention !

References I

Albarillo, F. (2014).

Language in social science databases: English versus non-english articles in jstor and scopus.

Behavioral & Social Sciences Librarian, 33(2):77–90.

Anderson, M. H. and Lemken, R. K. (2020).

Citation context analysis as a method for conducting rigorous and impactful literature reviews.

Organizational Research Methods, page 109442812096990.

References II

Bertin, M., Atanassova, I., Lariviere, V., and Gingras, Y. (2013).

The distribution of references in scientific papers: an analysis of the imrad structure.

In *Proceedings of the 14th ISSI Conference*, volume 591, page 603.

Bertin, M., Jonin, P., Armetta, F., and Atanassova, I. (2019).

Determining Citation Blocks using End-to-end Neural Coreference Resolution Model for Citation Context Analysis.

In *17th International Conference on Scientometrics & Informetrics*, volume 2 of *17th International Conference on Scientometrics & Informetrics ISSI2019*, page 2720, Rome, Italy. International Society on Scientometrics & Informetrics.

References III

- Collignon, A. and Cuxac, P. (2017).
Istex: des enrichissements au web de données.
I2D - Information, données and documents, 54(4):8–15.
- Engels, T. C. and Kulczycki, E. (2022).
Handbook on Research Assessment in the Social Sciences.
Edward Elgar Publishing, Cheltenham, UK.
- Gordin, M. D. (2015).
Scientific Babel: How Science Was Done Before and After Global English.
University of Chicago Press.

References IV

- Hosseini, A., Ghavimi, B., Boukhers, Z., and Mayr, P. (2019). Excite: A toolchain to extract, match and publish open literature references.
In Proceedings of the 18th Joint Conference on Digital Libraries, JCDL '19, page 432–433. IEEE Press.
- Joshi, M., Chen, D., Liu, Y., Weld, D. S., Zettlemoyer, L., and Levy, O. (2020). SpanBERT: Improving pre-training by representing and predicting spans.
Transactions of the Association for Computational Linguistics, 8:64–77.

References V

- Kamińska, A. (2017).
Plos one - a case study of citation analysis of research papers based on the data in an open citation index (the opencitations corpus).
- Liu, W. (2017).
The changing role of non-english papers in scholarly communication: Evidence from web of science's three journal citation indexes.
Learned Publishing, 30(2):115–123.
- Ritchie, A. (2009).
Citation context analysis for information retrieval.
PhD thesis, University of Cambridge, UK.

References VI

- Shotton, D. (2010).
Cito, the citation typing ontology.
Journal of Biomedical Semantics, 1(1):S6.
- Small, H. (1982).
Citation context analysis.
Progress in communication sciences, pages 287–310.
- Spiegel-Rosing, I. (1977).
Science studies: Bibliometric and content analysis.
Social Studies of Science, 7(1):97–113.

References VII

Teufel, S. and Elhadad, N. (2002).

Collection and linguistic processing of a large-scale corpus of medical articles.

In *Proceedings of the Third International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC'02)*, Las Palmas, Canary Islands - Spain. European Language Resources Association (ELRA).

Teufel, S., Siddharthan, A., and Tidhar, D. (2006).

An annotation scheme for citation function.

In *Proceedings of the 7th SIGdial Workshop on Discourse and Dialogue*, pages 80–87, Sydney, Australia. Association for Computational Linguistics.